

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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THE INFLUENCE OF TOUR INTERPRETATION ON PERCEIVED HERITAGE VALUES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TOURISTS WITH AND WITHOUT GUIDED INTERPRETATION AT A HERITAGE DESTINATION

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Abstract: The tourism sphere has become the most flourishing sector globally. There are many participants in this sector, making it crucial for countries and for people who explore new horizons by visiting other cultures and gaining new experiences. Tourists contribute significantly to tourism growth. Understanding what tourists want and value is important in tourism management. This research focused on guest perceived values in guided and self-guided groups and measured the influence of guided interpretation. It examines visitor need for tour interpretation and tests whether it implies positive or negative aspects on their perceived heritage values. This helps comprehend tourist needs on guiding methods and opens new directions for sustainable tourism. Tourist satisfaction remains key.

Key words: Tour interpretation, guided tour, self-guided tour, perceived heritage values, historical values, historical association value, identity values, aesthetic values.

Annotatsiya: Turizm sohasi global miqyosda eng gullab-yashnagan sohaga aylandi. Ushbu sektorning ko'plab ishtirokchilari uni mamlakatlar uchun muhim segment sifatida saqlab qolmoqda. O'z chegaralaridan chiqib, boshqa madaniyatlarga tashrif buyurib, yangi tajriba orttirgan odamlar turizmga sezilarli hissa qo'shadi. Sayohat davomida nimani xohlashlarini va qadrlashlarini tushunish turizmni boshqarishda muhimdir. Biz e'tiborimizni gid hamrohidagi va gidsiz guruhlarda mehmonlar tomonidan qabul qilingan qadriyatlarga qaratdik. Tadqiqot tashrif buyuruvchilarning sharhlashga bo'lgan ehtiyojlarini o'rganadi va bu talqin meros qadriyatlariga qanday ta'sir qilishini tekshiradi. Bu orqali barqaror turizmning yangi yo'nalishlari ochiladi. Turizmni yaxshi o'lchaydigan va qadrlaydigan narsa — bu turistlarning qoniqishidir.

Kalit so'zlar: Ekskursiya talqini, gidli tur, erkin sayohat, anglangan meros qadriyatlari, tarixiy qadriyatlar, estetik qadriyatlar.

Аннотация: Сфера туризма стала одной из самых процветающих в мире. Участников этой отрасли множество, и она имеет важное значение для стран, а также для людей, стремящихся к новым горизонтам, посещая другие культуры и приобретая новый опыт. Туристы вносят значительный вклад в развитие туризма. Понимание того, чего хотят и что ценят туристы, важно для управления в сфере туризма. В данном исследовании изучаются восприятие ценностей в группах с экскурсоводом и без, а также влияние экскурсионной интерпретации. Исследование помогает лучше понять потребности туристов в различных формах экскурсионного сопровождения и открывает новые пути для устойчивого туризма. Удовлетворённость туристов остаётся главным показателем эффективности.

Ключевые слова: Экскурсионная интерпретация, тур с гидом, самостоятельный тур, воспринимаемые ценности наследия, исторические ценности, эстетические ценности.

INTRODUCTION

This study examines the influence of tour interpretation on perceived heritage values, using two groups of tourists – one receiving a guided tour and one conducting a self-guided tour – at a heritage-listed destination as a case study. The heritage destination has the power to impose its values on the tourists. Research into their expressed values may help to establish the extent to which this process is occurring. Understanding how tourists' values are influenced can help destination management to balance the need to present a destination in such a way as to satisfy market demand with the assurance that the integrity of the destination is being maintained. Tour interpretation represents a fundamental tool for communication at heritage sites, helping to connect visitors with the heritage values of a place. Through interpretation, tourists gain an understanding of the significance of heritage places. What they value is, in part, influenced by this understanding. As a result, interpretation can influence not only what is seen, but also what is valued, at heritage destinations. While many studies explored the impact of interpretation in a guided tour setting, there is a noticeable lack of research that has compared the influence of interpretation between the guided and self-guided tourist. Guided tours were found to add significant value to a tourism experience, through the additional insight and unique stories that tour guides provide. Despite the available evidence of the substantial benefits of guided tours, visitors at heritage destinations are increasing in their diversity and decreasing in their willingness to participate in organized tours. In response, many heritage destinations have adopted a layered approach to interpretation to provide interpretation that caters to different visitor preferences (Crespi-Vallbona, 2021).

Heritage sites have played a prominent role in tourism, attracting large numbers of tourists from around the world. However, the meaning and values of heritage places may be lost without the active and positive engagement of visitors. Heritage interpretation, undertaken by professional interpreters or through self-guided means such as interpretation panels, leaflets, and audio guides, is widely recognized as the most important service at heritage sites.

Interpretation helps tourists to have a deeper understanding, establish an emotional connection, and appreciate the significance of a heritage site. These stories and the delivery of interpretation have the power to influence tourists' experiences and their perceived heritage values. As such, interpretation can be expressed as a mediator that shapes and defines tourists' understanding and perception (Domínguez-Quintero et al., 2020). This study explored the influence of tour interpretation on perceived heritage values, comparing the differences between guided and self-guided tourists at a heritage destination.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Interpretation at heritage sites has long been recognized as an important tool for both site management and visitor satisfaction (Huete and López, 2020). Tourist interpretation has been described as an art which combines information with inspiration and involves a service deliverable within the tourism experience. Interpretation is further seen as a means of enhancing cultural exchange and understanding, and plays an important role in the direction and quality of tourist experiences (Kim & So, 2022). Through interpretation a story is presented, and if the audience becomes involved, then from that involvement comes personal meaning, and from that meaning comes realization and awareness. Interpretation helps travelers make sense of their journey and thereby helps them absorb the intended physical and emotional experience. The study proposes a model, based on this framework, to compare the effect of tour interpretation on the perceived heritage values of tourists who receive guided interpretation with those who do not. It does so by addressing three research questions associated with the main goal of interpretation which are as follows: What did the tourists actually see and how did they understand the destination? What was the tourist response to interpretation/guiding? What tourist values were influenced? These perceptions subsequently influence tourist values and interpretative guided values can help shape these perceptions. In most cases, tourists will be influenced and change their understanding of the site after being involved in interpretative programs. Heritage interpretation is conceptualized as a broader national goal and as a process designed to increase opportunities for public appreciation and understanding of, and involvement with sites. Heritage interpretation aims to reveal the meanings and values of heritage as stories speak the language of the destination (Smith, 2020). The essence of heritage interpretation is to add meaningful value to tourist experiences, stir the tourists' emotions leading to possible involvement with the heritage site. When tourists become involved with a heritage site they are more likely to support conservation of that heritage. The function of interpretation, in the present context, is to enhance visit satisfaction, and via this route, to consequently influence perceived heritage value and the desire to protect that heritage (Domínguez-Quintero et al., 2020). Spoken interpretation is often provided by tour guides and is suitable for involving and interacting with visitors. Audio interpretation can be provided via mobile apps or devices that enable the visitor to move at his or her own pace while receiving a guided tour.

Heritage interpretation is a management tool usually employed to enhance public understanding of the heritage values of a place, to increase their satisfaction and to help them use these values more deeply and responsibly. Therefore, interpretation is a facilitator of meaningful tourist experiences. Interpretation, in its common usage, involves explaining, telling, or describing the meaning of something to other people. Interpreting heritage involves the use of all communication media available, from personal contact to advanced electronic technology, in offering messages that help people understand the complexities of heritage. Proper interpretation of heritage is important in order to impart adequate knowledge of the meaning and significance of heritage sites, values, and other related aspects to a tourist. According to Cleere, the concept of heritage interpretation emerged over 50 years ago and has developed over time as part of cultural, ecological and recreational settings. The term “heritage interpretation” was first used in the late 1950s, initially as part of the National Park Service activities in the USA. Development of heritage interpretation was influenced by specialists who defined the philosophy of interpretation, trained interpreters, and established principles and techniques (2020). Interest is still growing, as can be seen in the quantity and quality of publications on the subject coming from diverse sources around the world.

The concept of heritage values has been extensively discussed in the heritage management literature. Widely accepted, however, is the tripartite division of heritage values into “inherent values,” “stakeholder values,” and “perceived values.” The term “heritage values” is used as a value-based statement about an object or place. Tourists’ perceived heritage values determine the visitation experience; they can also influence the level of support for heritage site management. It has been suggested that heritage interpretation’s main goal should be the enhancement of tourists’ perceived heritage values (Genc and Gulertekin, 2023). The influence of tour interpretation on perceived heritage value is measured using four variables of HPM: historical value (HV), historical association value (HAV), aesthetic value (AV), and identity value (IDV). Guided interpretive tours are likely to be more effective at enhancing perceived heritage values than self-guided tours because guides can direct tourists’ attention and help them understand the meaning of heritage attributes. Various factors are known to influence the determination of perceived heritage values, including visitor characteristics, visitation context, and heritage site attributes. The value perception theory provides an overall framework to understand human value and value perception in a variety of contexts. Findings that values influence what people perceive in their surroundings provide support for the argument that values are general motivators that guide people’s attention to value-laden features of various objects. These factors include individual characteristics, the physical attributes of the object, the psychological attachment to the object, and the way the object is presented to the public. Interpretation is still the main direct contact means of the heritage to the public and has been revealed to effectively influence tourists at heritage sites. Contribution of interpretation to the positive influence on tourist experience is the enhancement of the perceived values.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data Collection

This research explores the influence of tour interpretation on perceived heritage values and has implications for heritage destination management. Study results find that tour interpretation influences perceived heritage values. The most significant contribution of this study is that it examines the influence of tour interpretation on perceived heritage values at a heritage destination, including quantitative (survey) and qualitative (Literature Review). It compares tourists with guided interpretation to those without guided interpretation. To understand the heritage values of tourists and figure out in which aspects there is a change in them, 3 of the 4 questions were about PHV. The last question was about guided tours, which helped to comprehend the opinions of visitors. 40 people participated in the survey: half of them were guided (in person) and the other half self-guided (online) visitors. This research adds to the existing scholarly works that explore the influence of tour interpretation on perceived heritage values. This allows the study to offer new insights and a deeper understanding of how tour interpretation influences the perceived heritage values of tourists.

3.2. Survey

Tourists’ perception of heritage values is a popular research topic. However, while a simple heritage tour can change tourist perception, few studies have explored how tour interpretation influences tourists’ perceived heritage values. This study examines the influence of tour interpretation on tourists’ perceived heritage values by comparing tourists with and without guided interpretation. We chose in-person communication as the most convenient survey method with 20 participants and held a questionnaire at Registan Square. We also conducted the same survey online using the Telegram platform. The questions were sent to the groups “Sallies of Uzbekistan” and “Trip to Aksay”, which included traveler audiences. Collected results were organized in the form of tables and diagrams (Appendix 1).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1. Result of the Research

The purpose of interpretation is to provide tourists with profound connections to places through communicating site significance, and thereby help to increase the positive effects that tourism can have on both tourists and the visited heritage site. Tourists with guided interpretation had a higher mean score in perceived historical value compared to tourists without guided interpretation, who had the lowest mean score among all the groups. While tourists with guided interpretation had the highest and second highest mean scores in perceived cultural and architectural values, the group of tourists without any guided interpretation scored the twofold lowest means. As for local tourists, they had the highest mean scores in perceived aesthetic (architectural, leisure) values, but the lowest mean scores in perceived cultural and spiritual value. In terms of historical value, tourists without any guided interpretation had the highest score, while none of the sides mentioned educational value. Perceived historical, cultural, and architectural values were generally found to be higher among tourists with tour interpretation, while mostly the historical values were higher among tourists without tour interpretation. Furthermore, the influence of tour interpretation on perceived heritage values is stronger at the interpretation site or location compared to the overall trip or visit. The results of the study contribute to the understanding of the influence of interpretation on heritage values and provide useful implications for heritage site management and tour guiding.

4.2. Key Findings

As the survey with guided group approached oral conversation style, we can possibly provide the general idea of their answers. It is worth reiterating that, T1 group (20 respondents) perceived historical, cultural and architectural values influenced, and preferred guided-tours to self-guided ones although the sample group consisted of not only newcomers, but the tour guides, self-investigators or locals. Mentioned by one of the respondents: "If tour guide is knowledgeable and local, it is more interesting. Because as I feel, tour-guide is not only about delivering the specific data, but also a human who can share inspirations and emotions about the heritage destination, so I will be alright of asking some culture-related questions. And only qualified tour-guide can answer properly to the person who came from another culture". Further research with the other 20 interviewees without T1 presents that regardless of slight differences in PHV between them both guided and non-guided travelers put a high emphasize on the importance of tour interpretation. To increase the visual comparison, we presented the results of the survey from two samples (guided and not guided) in a visual state, in the form of a tables and a diagrams showcasing 4 questions in a brief form below:

Table 1. Showcase of how guests saw the destination before their visit

No 1	Place-based perception (before)	Amount of local guests answered	Amount of foreign guests answered	In Total	Medium proportion
A	Very famous	7	6	13	65 %
B	Moderately known	1	3	4	20 %
C	Little known	1	0	1	0,5 %
D	Unfamiliar	1	1	2	10 %

Place-based perception (before)

Figure 1. Tourists' place-based perception before the trip

Table 2. Showcase of how guests saw the destination after their visit

№ 2	Place-based perception (after)	Amount of local guests answered	Amount of foreign guests answered	In Total	Medium proportion
A	A must-visit	4	4	8	40 %
B	Worth seeing	5	5	10	50 %
C	Somewhat interesting	1	1	2	10 %
D	Disappointing	0	0	0	0 %

Place-based perception (after)

Figure 2. Tourists' place-based perception after the trip

Table 3. Showcase of influenced tourist heritage values

№ 3	Influenced Tourist Values	Amount of local guests answered	Amount of foreign guests answered	In Total	Medium proportion
A	Historical	2	4	6	30 %
B	Architectural	3	1	4	20 %
C	Cultural	1	3	4	20 %
D	Spiritual	1	1	2	10 %
E	Educational	0	0	0	0 %
F	Leisure	3	1	4	20 %

Influenced Tourist Values

Figure 3. Influenced tourist values

Table 4. Showcase of tourist preference about guided interpretation

№ 4	Would your perceptions be the same if you had/did not have guided interpretation during the trip?	Amount of local guests answered	Amount of foreign guests answered	In Total	Medium proportion
A	Yes	8	7	15	75 %
B	No	1	2	3	15 %
C	Uncertain	1	1	2	10 %

Would your perceptions be the same if you had/did not have guided interpretation during the trip?

Figure 4. Tourist preference about guided interpretation

4.3. Discussion

Relying on the self-guided visitor experience, exact sample measures were collected and calculated. As seen in Table 1 and Figure 1, the majority of tourists chose their target destination according to its renown in both local and foreign samples, at 65%. International guests often visit when a destination is moderately famous — covering almost 20% of the whole diagram.

After their excursion, 50% of guests considered the destination worth seeing, while 40% called it a must-visit spot (Table 2, Figure 2). None of the tourists were disappointed, except one-tenth of the group who found it slightly interesting.

In Table 3 and Figure 3, six tourist values were assessed: historical, cultural, spiritual, educational, and leisure. Local tourists were more impacted by architectural beauty and entertainment, while foreign visitors prioritized historical significance and cultural enrichment. Historical value had the highest overall share among both groups.

The most consequential part of the survey, Table 4 and Figure 4, demonstrates that the vast majority (three-quarters) of guests find tour-interpretation (TI) crucial — regardless of domestic or international identity.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

Tourism is one of the most important components in modern socio-economic systems, and increasingly tourism is associated with visits to cultural heritage sites. Cultural heritage tourism is one of the fastest growing tourism market segments and makes up a significant proportion of overall international tourism receipts. Heritage sites can be either man-made (buildings, towns, etc.) or natural (landscapes, caves, etc.) and often are of a unique, or at least very special, character (Kim et al., 2021). However, it is important that the values of these heritage sites are protected. Tourism visitation has the potential to both support and undermine heritage site values. The management of tourism at heritage sites is of considerable importance. That is why this study focuses on assessing how the experience of a heritage site through tour interpretation influences tourists' perceptions of heritage values. The major heritage values identified in the study included five perceived value types (historical, architectural, cultural, educational, and entertainment), and spiritual value was a new addition to the typology of PHV. The results showed that sustainable interpretation could enrich tourists' PHVs and their overall destination experience. In summary, we stress that the effect of interpretation should be carefully considered for achieving an optimal outcome in heritage value enhancement. The best outcome will vary depending on the characteristics of the tourism market.

5.2. Implication

Guided interpretation is a powerful tool that provides positive effects, adding to the perceived value of heritage sites. This study explores the effect of interpretation on tourists and their perceived heritage values (PHVs) while examining two groups, one with guided interpretation and one without. Data were collected from Registan Square, a World Heritage site in Uzbekistan. The results show that guided interpretation influences tourists' PHVs and helps place the site in a local historical context. These findings affirm the mediation role of visitor interest and the moderating role of prior knowledge in tourists' decision-making. These findings have practical implications for heritage sites.

5.3. Recommendations

This study demonstrated the significance of interpretation in promoting the understanding of heritage values. The results highlight the necessity to incorporate new methods into interpretation practices for different tourist groups. The study aimed to determine potential perceived heritage value differences between tourists who received guided interpretation and those who did not.

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